

SCHOOL-BASED FACILITY AND FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AS CORRELATES OF QUALITY ADMINISTRATION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the relationship between school-based facility and financial management and quality administration in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A correlational research design was adopted to determine the nature and degree of association between principals' administrative skills and teachers' performance. The population comprised 355 principals and 8,228 teachers across 355 public secondary schools. A sample of 823 respondents, representing 15% of the population, was drawn using cluster and simple random sampling techniques, resulting in 77 schools and 702 teacher participants. Data were collected through two self-developed instruments: the School-Based Management Scale (SBMS) and the Quality Administration Scale (QAS). The SBMS measured facility and financial management, while the QAS assessed administration of staff, curriculum, facilities, and students. Both instruments included demographic sections and Likert-scale items. Reliability, determined via Cronbach's Alpha, yielded coefficients of .734 (SBMS) and .807 (QAS), indicating acceptable internal consistency. Validity was ensured through expert review. Data were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC), and hypotheses were tested with associated z-tests. Findings were interpreted based on the classification of relationship strength, providing insights into how effective facility and financial management correlates with the quality of school administration in public secondary schools. The study recommends among others that school facility management should be accorded priority also in school-based management system, in addition to regular supply from the school board or government for quality administration.

Keywords: School-Based, Facility Management, Financial Management, Quality Administration, Public Secondary Schools, Rivers State.

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INTRODUCTION

Effective administration of public secondary schools is crucial for achieving the desirable educational outcomes, equity and efficiency. In Nigeria, the quality of school administration is increasingly being linked to how well schools manage their physical facilities and financial resources (Ololube, 2017). School-based facility and financial management constitute the

foundational pillars that support the daily functioning and long-term sustainability of educational institutions. According to Akpan and Udosen (2019) and Ofoegbu (2020), without adequate infrastructure and prudent financial stewardship, public schools are constrained in delivering quality education, which impedes overall institutional performance and student attainment.

School facilities refer to the physical structures, learning environments, utilities, instructional materials, and other tangible resources that foster teaching and learning processes (UNESCO, 2017), and in public secondary schools, quality facility management guarantees that classrooms are safe, adequately ventilated and conducive to learning, laboratories are functional, and essential services such as sanitation and electricity are consistently available (Adewale & Yusuf, 2021). Equally, poorly maintained facilities have been associated with low teacher morale, higher student distraction, increased absenteeism and diminished academic achievement (Earthman, 2018; Ololube, 2017). Therefore, facilities management is not a peripheral administrative task but a core function that directly influences the instructional climate and the overall quality of education.

Financial management in schools encompasses budgeting, accounting, resource allocation, and financial reporting practices that ensure the judicious use of funds (Eze & Okere, 2018). Public secondary schools in Rivers State operate within constrained fiscal environments characterized by inconsistent government subventions, limited internally generated revenue, and competing demands for scarce resources (Nwankwo, 2019). In such settings, effective financial management practices, which include transparent budgeting processes, internal controls and accountability mechanisms are essential to optimizing available resources and minimizing wastage or misappropriation (Obi & Anigbogu, 2020). When financial resources are managed poorly, critical areas such as teacher welfare, instructional materials and school maintenance suffer undermine administrative quality.

Empirical studies suggest that there is a significant relationship between facility provision and financial management with school effectiveness. For instance, Adeyemi (2017) found that schools with adequate facilities and transparent financial practices recorded higher levels of academic performance, improved stakeholder confidence, and enhanced teacher retention. Similarly, Udo and Amadi (2019) reported that poor infrastructure and weak financial oversight in Nigerian secondary schools contributed to teacher dissatisfaction, low student engagement, and administrative inefficiencies. These findings emphasized that facility and financial management are not isolated administrative concerns but interrelated variables that collectively shape the quality of school leadership and management.

Public secondary schools in Nigeria in particular have over the years grapple with dilapidated classroom blocks, insufficient learning aids and irregular remuneration for staff, which place immense pressure on school administrators (Jatto & Onyeje, 2021). As such, educational policymakers have advocated for greater autonomy at the school level to enable heads and governing councils to make timely decisions regarding facility maintenance and financial planning (Federal Ministry of Education, 2022). Yet, achieving meaningful autonomy requires capacity building, robust oversight, and community involvement to ensure that decentralized management translates into quality administration.

The theoretical underpinning for examining facility and financial management as correlates of quality administration is grounded in the Resource Dependency Theory (RDT) and the School Effectiveness Framework (SEF). RDT posits that organizations depend on external and internal resources to survive and thrive, making the management of these resources critical for organizational success (Pfeffer & Salancik, 2003). In the school context, this means that

administrators must effectively mobilize and deploy facilities and funds to enhance educational outcomes. The SEF further suggests that inputs such as infrastructure, leadership, and financial resources interact to influence school performance (Lezotte & Jacoby, 2020). Applying these frameworks to Rivers State's public secondary schools highlights the importance of examining how facility and financial management practices correlate with the quality of school administration.

Thus, understanding school-based facility and financial management is fundamental to advancing quality administration in public secondary schools. As Rivers State endeavors to improve its educational landscape, investigating these correlates is timely and necessary for informing policy, strengthen administrative practices and enhancing student achievement.

Statement of the Problem

In Rivers State, many schools face significant challenges related to inadequate facilities and poor financial management, which undermine the quality of school administration. Public secondary schools classrooms are often overcrowded, laboratories and libraries are poorly equipped and essential utilities such as electricity and water are inconsistently available. These infrastructural deficits impede teaching and learning processes, lower student engagement, and contribute to poor academic outcomes.

Financial management also remains a critical concern, as many school administrators lack the capacity for effective budgeting, accountability, and resource allocation. Delayed government funding, misappropriation of resources, and lack of transparency exacerbate the situation, leading to inefficiencies in school operations. Consequently, administrators struggle to maintain functional facilities, support teacher welfare, and implement school development programs effectively.

In spite these challenges, there is limited empirical research investigating the extent to which school-based facility and financial management practices influence the quality of administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. This study therefore sought to fill this gap by examining how these factors correlate with administrative effectiveness, providing evidence to inform policy and improve school management practices.

Purpose of this Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate school-based facility and financial management as correlates of quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study was designed to:

- Assess the relationship between school-based facility management and quality administration in public secondary education schools in Rivers State.
- Determine the relationship between school-based finance management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

This study is guided by two research questions:

- What is the relationship between school-based facility management and quality administration in public secondary education schools in Rivers State?
- What is the relationship between school-based finance management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to further guide the study:

- There is no significant relationship between school-based facility management and quality administration in public secondary education schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant relationship between school-based finance management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State

CONCEPTUALIZATION

Quality Administration

Quality administration in public secondary schools refers to the systematic planning, organization, coordination and control of human and material resources and their activities to achieve the goals of education efficiently and effectively. This also includes leadership practices, policy implementation, resource management and decision-making processes that collectively shape the school environment and influence student learning outcomes (Ofoegbu, 2020; Ololube, 2017).

Quality school administration is often evaluated in terms of leadership effectiveness, staff motivation, curriculum implementation and the ability to maintain a conducive learning environment (Akpan & Udosen, 2019). A key indicator of quality administration is the extent in which School Heads manage human, material and financial resources to achieve set objectives.

The quality of administration is also linked to the management of school facilities. Functional classrooms, well-equipped laboratories, libraries and recreational areas do not only enhance teaching and learning but also reflect the competence and commitment of school administrators (Adewale & Yusuf, 2021). Administrators who ensure the proper maintenance and utilization of these facilities promote an enabling environment that supports both academic and extracurricular activities. In contrast, the neglect of facilities often leads to student disengagement, teacher dissatisfaction, and overall institutional inefficiency (Earthman, 2018).

Financial management is another critical component of quality administration. Administrators are responsible for budgeting, allocation of funds, monitoring expenditures, and ensuring transparency in financial operations (Eze & Okere, 2018). Inadequate financial management practices compromise the school's ability to provide essential services, pay staff salaries on time and implement development projects. Quality administration further involves adherence to educational policies and regulatory frameworks set by government authorities. Compliance with the National Policy on Education ensures that schools uphold standards in curriculum delivery, staff recruitment, and infrastructure provision (Federal Ministry of Education, 2022). Effective administrators also prioritize professional development for teachers, engage in regular monitoring and evaluation of school activities, and promote innovative approaches to problem-solving.

Effective administrators or school leaders who engage in strategic planning, promote accountability and raise participatory decision-making, creates atmosphere of collaboration among teachers, students and the community (Lezotte & Jacoby, 2020). Therefore, quality administration is critical in ensuring that schools deliver educational services in line and to meet national standards, promotes equity and stand-in holistic student development.

School-Based Facility Management and Quality Administration of Secondary Schools

Effective school-based facility management is integral to the quality administration of secondary schools because the physical environment directly shapes teaching, learning and overall organizational performance. School facilities in the context of this study encompasses classrooms, laboratories, libraries, sanitation, furniture and outdoor spaces are foundational educational inputs that influence students' academic engagement and educators' instructional effectiveness (Idris et al., 2025; Ige & Aloh, 2025). Quality administration, in turn, refers to the systematic planning, organizing, directing and controlling of human and material resources with the goal of achieving educational objectives (Olaifa et al., 2025).

The literature establishes that poorly managed school facilities can undermine the quality of education delivery. Empirical research in Nigeria and other African contexts demonstrates relationships between physical infrastructure conditions and educational outcomes. For example, investigations in South East Nigeria found that the provision of administrative, instructional and recreational facilities significantly correlated with teachers' job effectiveness is a key component of quality administration and student success (Nwogwugwu & Obinna, 2024). Likewise, inadequate management of physical facilities in Kano State public secondary schools was shown to negatively affect students' learning, underscoring the broader impact that facility quality has on academic performance (Kakaba & Emechebe, 2025).

School facilities influence not only academic outcomes but also the capacity of administrators to perform effectively. Administrators responsible for planning and oversight must account for maintenance and strategic resource allocation to sustain conducive learning environments. A study on public senior secondary schools in Rivers State reported that regular maintenance of classrooms and audit mechanisms is associated with more effective school administration, suggesting that proactive facilities management supports overall institutional performance (Nwuke & Nwanguma, 2025).

In spite of its importance, facility management faces significant challenges, particularly in developing countries. Research in Anambra State identified structural and administrative constraints such as inadequate supervision time, poor power supply, negative staff attitudes, and insufficient funding as barriers to effective facilities management (Obi, 2025). These challenges often force school leaders into reactive maintenance approaches, compromising long-term quality administration and disrupting teaching processes (Ogbuka, as cited in Olaifa et al., 2025). Financial limitations compel many schools to prioritize immediate operational needs over preventive maintenance, which ultimately increases repair costs and degrades the learning environment.

Another challenge relates to stakeholder engagement. In Katsina State, community involvement in managing educational facilities was found to be minimal, which limited the development of essential infrastructure and negatively impacted teaching and learning activities (Sanda & Batagarawa, 2025). Strengthening partnerships with parents, community members, and

education quality assurance bodies can enhance resource mobilization and accountability in facility management.

The quality administration of secondary schools increasingly incorporates concepts from Total Quality Management and School-Based Management (SBM), emphasizes participatory planning, accountability and transparent use of resources. For instance, integrative management models that coordinate planning, implementation, supervision, and evaluation of facilities have been proposed to improve educational quality in junior high contexts, highlighting the potential for such frameworks to be adapted for secondary education (Adriansah et al., 2025; Digdowniseiso, 2024).

School-Based Finance Management and Quality Administration of Secondary Schools

Effective school-based finance management is fundamental in the quality administration of secondary schools because it directly influences resource allocation, accountability, and the overall achievement of educational goals. Finance management in education involves planning, organizing, controlling, and monitoring financial resources to ensure that educational activities are conducted efficiently and effectively (John, 2025). Within secondary schools, principals and school management committees are often tasked with financial decision-making, making their competence in financial planning and controls fundamental to institutional performance.

One major aspect of school-based finance management is the principals' ability to manage funds through budgeting, control and accountability practices. These practices help to ensure that available resources are used prudently, which in turn supports improved school administration outcomes by promoting accountability and efficient resource utilization (Manafa, 2025). Similarly, principals' budget management practices in Oyo State were found to have a significant positive relationship with secondary school performance, indicating that well-planned financial management enhances school outcomes (Oyeniran et al., 2025).

The relationship between financial accountability and school performance underscores that transparent financial practices build stakeholder trust and foster more effective educational administration. A study from Zambia found a strong correlation between financial accountability by school managers and positive educational outcomes; schools with financially accountable managers demonstrated better performance, partly due to inclusive decision-making that involved teachers, parents, and community members (Njobvu & Kabaso, 2025). This highlights the need for transparent financial processes that are understood and supported by all stakeholders, not just school administrators.

Another important dimension is the role of school-based management committees (SBMCs) in finance management. In the North-West zone of Nigeria, research found that SBMC participation in providing funds and ensuring school security contributes to improving the quality of secondary education. When SBMC members are actively involved in financial mobilization and oversight, schools can better leverage community support to supplement government funds, enhancing the quality and sustainability of educational services (Umar & Kwashabawa, 2025).

However, challenges persist. Many secondary schools face difficulties such as delayed disbursement of funds, inadequate financial controls, and limited training for principals in financial management. For example, studies in Kaduna State have shown that although schools generate supplementary funds through PTA levies and other activities, issues like untimely funding, lack of ICT training for financial record-keeping, and weak internal audit systems limit

the effectiveness of financial management practices (Aliyu, 2018). These constraints can result in poor planning, misallocation of resources, and ultimately, suboptimal administrative quality.

To address these challenges, professional development and capacity-building for school administrators are essential. Training initiatives that strengthen principals' budgeting, accounting, and financial reporting skills have been recommended to improve the quality of school finance management (Akumah & Onele, 2024). Governments and education authorities should also emphasize participatory budgeting, regular auditing, and stakeholder involvement in financial decision-making processes to enhance accountability and support quality administration.

Thus, school-based finance management is a vital component of quality administration in secondary schools. Effective budgeting, accountability, and collaborative financial practices enhance resource utilization, build trust, and improve educational outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design, which is appropriate for examining the relationship between two or more variables. This design was considered suitable because it enabled the researcher to determine the nature and degree of relationship between principals' administrative skills and teachers' performance in mission schools.

The population of the study comprised all the three hundred and fifty-five (355) principals and eight thousand two hundred and twenty-eight (8,228) teachers in the three hundred and fifty-five (355) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. From this population, a sample size of eight hundred and twenty-three (823) respondents, representing 15% of the total population, was selected. The sample consisted of 121 principals and 702 teachers.

A cluster sampling technique was employed to group the respondents into the three senatorial zones of Rivers State-Rivers East, Rivers West, and Rivers South-East. Subsequently, a simple random sampling technique was used to select schools from two Local Government Areas in each senatorial zone. This procedure resulted in a total of seventy-seven (77) public senior secondary schools, from which seven hundred and two (702) teachers participated in the study.

Data for the study were collected using two self-developed instruments titled "School-Based Management Scale (SBMS) and Quality Administration Scale (QAS)". The SBMS was structured into two subsections reflecting the major variables of the study: school-based facility management and school-based finance management. Similarly, the QAS comprised four subsections covering the administration of staff personnel, school curriculum, school facilities, and student personnel. Each instrument consisted of two sections: Section 'A' elicited demographic information from the respondents, while Section 'B' contained the research items.

Responses were measured using a modified Likert scale with four response options: Strongly Agree (4 points), Agree (3 points), Disagree (2 points), and Strongly Disagree (1 point). The reliability of the instruments was determined using the Cronbach's Alpha method to assess internal consistency. The instruments were administered once to 20 teachers who were not included in the study sample. The reliability coefficients obtained were .734 for the SBMS and .807 for the QAS, indicating acceptable reliability levels. To establish the validity of the instruments, draft copies were submitted to the research supervisor and experts in Test and Measurement for scrutiny. Their suggestions regarding content coverage and clarity were incorporated into the final versions of the instruments.

The researchers assisted by two trained research assistants, administered the instruments. The assistants were adequately briefed on the purpose of the study and the administration procedures to ensure effective distribution and retrieval of the questionnaires. Data collected were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC), while the null hypotheses were tested using the z-test associated with the PPMCC. The strength of the relationships was interpreted using the classification levels provided by Nwankwo (2013).

RESULTS

Research Question One: What is the relationship between school-based facility management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between school-based facility management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Moment Correlation coefficient analysis and z-ratio on the relationship between school-based facility and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State

Variables	N	Df.	r-cal	z-ratio	r-crit.	Sig	P-critical	Decision
School-Based Facility Quality Administration	823	821	.877	29.23	1.96	.008	.05	Statistically significant

From the result of the above table, the correlation coefficient ($r = .877$) between school-based facility management and quality administration is very strong and positive. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.77$) indicates that 77% of quality administration can be explained by school-based facility management. With the degree of freedom of 821, the calculated z-ratio value of 29.23 is greater than the z-critical value of 1.96. Also, the significant value of .008 ($p < .01$) reveals a significant relationship. Based on the result, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between school-based facility management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between school-based finance management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between school-based finance management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Moment Correlation coefficient analysis and z-ratio on the relationship between school-based finance and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State

Variables	N	Df	r-cal	z-ratio	r-crit.	Sig	P-critical	Decision
School-Based Finance Quality Administration	823	821	.811	27.03	1.96	.006	.05	Statistically significant

From the result of the above table, the correlation coefficient ($r = .811$) between school-based finance management and quality administration is very strong and positive. The coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.66$) indicates that 66% of quality administration can be explained by school-based finance management. With the degree of freedom of 821, the calculated z-ratio value of 27.03 is greater than the z-critical value of 1.96. Also, the significant value of .006 ($p < .01$) reveals a significant relationship. Based on that, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between school-based finance management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION

School-based Facility Management and Quality Administration in Public Secondary Schools

School-based facility management has a high significant relationship with quality administration in public secondary schools Rivers State. School facilities include the permanent and non-permanent structure as well as the facilities and equipment such as building, furniture, vehicles, laboratories, libraries, playground, books, furniture etc. These facilities play important roles in quality administration in secondary schools as they constitute the physical aspect of school administration that enhance learning and contribute to students' performance. They are also contributive to school administration to enhance school-based management.

This finding supports the finding of this study because it revealed that the school facilities are directly or indirectly connected to the school curriculum. It is therefore, almost impossible for the school to record a perceived high level of administrative performance if the things required for teaching and learning are not put in place. In the same vein, Idris et al. (2025) and Ige and Aloh (2025) upheld that high level of students learning outcome may not be guaranteed where school facilities such as school site planning in structural space planning, administrative space planning, space of convenience and circulation are not properly ventilated and not spacious enough for use.

It follows therefore that school management of facilities becomes one of the key areas demanding attention from school administration. Nwogwugwu and Obinna (2024) found that the provision of administrative, instructional and recreational facilities significantly correlated with teachers' job effectiveness is a key component of quality administration and student success.

School-based Finance Management and Quality Administration in Public Secondary Schools

There is a high positive and significant relationship between school-based finance management and quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. John (2025) stated that in the management of school finance, accountability is greatly needed. In education, accountability means a report reflecting or balance between the resource input and result output. Every principal should be disciplined, honest, responsive, productive, expert in goal-setting and evaluation. The principals should be able to keep records which are tasks of education manager in managing education fund.

Aliyu (2018) supported the claim that school-based finance management is a vital component of quality administration in secondary schools. Effective budgeting, accountability,

and collaborative financial practices enhance resource utilization, build trust, and improve educational outcomes. These findings give credence to the finding of this study which revealed that there is high positive and significant relationship between school-based finance management and quality administration. The relationship is consolidated in school budgeting, financial record keeping, allocation, accountability just like Oyeniran et al. (2025) has pointed that school-based finance management is necessary because no school runs without funds. The principals should control the finances of the schools. The principals must exercise relative control over how money is spent on recurrent and capital projects. Similarity in the findings of other scholars and the finding of this study point to the fact that finance is a very crucial aspect of any organization and management is of paramount concern to everyone in an organization.

CONCLUSION

This study successfully evaluated the relationship between school-based facility and financial management and quality administration in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, and the findings indicated that effective school-based facility and financial management significantly correlate with quality administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Proper management of school facilities ensures an enabling environment for teaching and learning, while sound financial practices enhance the availability of resources necessary for smooth school operations. The study further revealed that principals who demonstrate competence in managing facilities and finances tend to promote better staff performance, improved curriculum delivery and efficient student personnel administration. These results underscore the importance of equipping school leaders with the skills and knowledge required for effective facility and financial management. As a result, policymakers and educational stakeholders should emphasize the need for training programs and monitoring mechanisms that will strengthen school-based management practices, to promote enhanced quality administration and overall educational outcomes in public secondary schools across the state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were given:

- School facility management should be accorded priority also in school-based management system, in addition to regular supply from the school board or government for quality administration.
- School-based finance management require sufficient fund to carry out its activities. However, due to insufficiency in the financial allocation to the educational sector, it becomes imperative that school administrators discover other sources of revenue to keep the school and balanced budget.

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